

Determination of the mass concentration of suspended particles in the atmosphere: A protocol for students in Environmental Engineering and related fields

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1. Introduction

The potential of airborne particles to cause adverse health effects is strongly influenced by their size. During inhalation, particles with an aerodynamic diameter of up to 100 μm may enter the human respiratory tract. However, only the finer particles, typically those with diameters below 5 μm , are able to penetrate deeply into the lungs and reach the alveolar region. These smaller particles are now widely recognized as posing the greatest health risks due to their enhanced capacity for deposition within the respiratory system and their association with various respiratory and cardiovascular diseases. Consequently, accurately characterizing particle size has become a fundamental aspect of atmospheric particulate matter assessment. In this context, measuring only total suspended particles (TSP) or total suspended matter (TSM) is no longer sufficient; instead, particulate matter must be separated and quantified according to specific size fractions.

In order to understand the effects of particles that enter the human respiratory system, it is necessary to use equipment that simulates the efficiency with which particles enter through the nose and mouth, until they reach the areas of the human body most susceptible to injury.

In the 1980s and 1990s, the International Standards Organization (ISO) defined a set of conventions for the sampling of particles with health effects, both in ambient air and in workplace settings. According to the guidelines established by this organization, the thoracic fraction is defined as the mass fraction of total inhalable particles that enter the respiratory system beyond the larynx, reaching the chest. When referenced to the total suspended particles in the atmosphere, the thoracic fraction is represented by a lognormal cumulative function with a median aerodynamic diameter of 10 μm and a geometric standard deviation of 1.5. On the other hand, in 1987, the Environmental Protection Agency (EPA, USA) adopted the PM_{10} convention for sampling particles that penetrate the respiratory system up to the chest. The main difference between the two conventions is that the curve defining the collection efficiency for the PM_{10} fraction has a steeper slope for an equivalent aerodynamic diameter greater than 10 μm compared to that of the thoracic fraction. Similarly, the respirable fraction is defined, which corresponds to the fraction of inhaled particles that can penetrate into the

alveolar region. In terms of monitoring, this fraction corresponds to the PM_{2.5} particles. These conventions, PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}, in terms of monitoring, correspond to the particle fractions that pass through a sampling head with a 50% cut-off efficiency at aerodynamic diameters of 10 and 2.5 μm, respectively.

The objective of this work is to measure the mass concentration of suspended particles in the atmosphere (PM₁₀ or PM_{2.5}) using a low-flow sampler that operates according to the method defined by the European Union.

Figure 1 ISO Conventions for Atmospheric Particle Sampling.

2. Experimental procedure

- Weigh 2 quartz fiber filters (e.g., Whatman QMA), previously placed in the weighing room, in a controlled environment (temperature around 20 °C and relative humidity around 50 %), for at least 24 hours before starting the weighing, using a balance with a sensitivity of 0.001 mg.
- Place one filter in the filter holder of the sampler and remove it, storing it to serve as a blank. Place a new filter in the filter holder and place it in the corresponding sampler. The process of placing the filter in the holder should be done with utmost care to avoid

damaging the filter, as any loss of material or any hole will significantly decrease the accuracy of the measurement.

- Turn on the device and check if the sampling flow rate is within the appropriate range.
- Program the controller for a 24-hour sampling period.
- After sampling, retrieve the report saved in the sampler's memory and record the sampled volume, as well as the average temperature and atmospheric pressure.
- Disassemble the filter holder, remove the filter, and transfer it to the weighing room.
- After at least 24 hours, perform a new weighing.

Figura 2 Schematic representation and operation principle of a PM₁₀/PM_{2.5} low volume sampler.

3. Report

In the report, the calculation of the mass concentration of suspended particles in the atmosphere with aerodynamic diameters less than 10 μm or 2.5 μm, depending on the sampling inlet used, should be included, both under the sampling conditions and under normalized conditions.

The mass concentration of particles in the atmosphere can be calculated using the following formula:

$$C_{\text{sampling}} = \frac{m_{\text{filter}} - m_{\text{blank}}}{V_{\text{sampled}}}$$

Where:

- C_{sampling} = Mass concentration of particles in the air during the sampling (in $\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)
- m_{filter} = Mass of the filter after sampling (in μg)
- m_{blank} = Mass of the blank filter (in μg)
- V_{sampled} = Volume of air sampled (in m^3), which can be calculated as:

$$V_{\text{sampled}} = Q_{\text{sampling}} \times t_{\text{sampling}}$$

Where:

- Q_{sampling} = Flow rate (in L/min or m^3/h)
- t_{sampling} = Sampling time (in hours)